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IMPACT OF EDUCATION STATUS, RELIGIOUS KNOWLEDGE AND FAMILY ECONOMY ON THE PRACTICING PRAYER STUDENTS FOR PRIMARY SCHOOL IN SETIU DISTRICT, TERENGGANU MALAYSIA

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Abstract

Prayer is a religious pillar where prayer is the greatest of worship that brings the servant closer to his Lord and it is the steadfastness of the relationship of the creature and its creator. The solat according to syarak is defined as a few words and deeds commenced with takbir and endorsed with greetings and with the conditions specified. This study was conducted to determine the effectiveness of educational status, religious knowledge and family economy on student prayer practice primary school in Setiu District. Total sample 175 secondary school students (level two) of the study. Data were analyzed using IBM-SPSS-AMOS (SEM) program version 21.0. The findings indicate that the educational status, religious knowledge and family economy on student prayer practice primary school. Furthermore, Inference analysis findings also show educational status, religious knowledge and family economy, have a positive and significant influence on student prayer practice. This shows that family education, especially in religious knowledge and economic family, plays a role in the practice of prayer in primary schools. In conclusion, the implications of this research, the researchers are aware of the need for cooperation from the school to emphasize the students on the practice of prayer in their daily lives. Although the level of education and family economics is a factor in the practice of prayer in this study, the role of teachers helps to overcome them.

Keywords: Structural Equation Modeling (SEM), Education Status, Religious Knowledge, Family Economic, Prayer Practice.

Introduction

Prayers are the pillars of religion where prayer is the greatest of worship that brings the slaves to their Lord and is the steadfastness of the relationship of the creatures and their creators (Maimon & Mohd Sukki, 2015). The solat according to shari'ah is defined as some words and deeds commenced with takbir and endorsed with greetings and with the specified conditions (Mukhlas, 2017). The five-day prayer is obligatory on the Muslim ummah and the obligations do not fall as long as life on the body. Word of the Prophet S.A.W. means "The prayer is the pillar of religion, whoever sets up prayers, indeed he has upholds religion and whoever abandons the solat actually he demeans religion".

Indeed, the act of abandoning this prayer is the most difficult case because it is a pillar of all religious affairs as it is the relationship between a servant and his Creator, Allah SWT. It's bad for one's treatment to be influenced by his prayers. If the prayer is good, it is done with perfection that includes aspects of harmoniousness, condition, and understanding and then willfully it will prevent a person from being abusive (Abdul Rashid & Herry Rena, 2016). This is the answer to the various problems that arise in each individual. Prayer is also the most important and important worship that is first reviewed and judged by God S.W.T on Judgment Day. If our prayers are good and perfect then all other worship will be perfect. On the other hand, if the prayer

is not perfect then it will be further examination of other worships ie fasting, zakat, pilgrimage and so forth. Word of the Prophet S.A.W: Meaning:

Abu Dawud narrated to us that he said, Harun (son of Ismail al-Khazzaj) told us, he said, Tell us Hammam from Qatadah, Al-Hasan, Khuraist bin Qubaishah, he said: I came to Medina, I said: Allah bless me in a good place, then tell me the hadiths which you have heard from the Messenger of Allah, may Allah be pleased with me, said: I heard the Messenger of Allah (may peace be upon him) saying: The first one from a slave on the Day of Judgment is the prayer. When the prayers are good then good is the whole practice but if the prayer is broken then it breaks the whole practice. (Hammam said: I do not know from this problem of Qatadah or from other narratives, if in the prayer fardu not perfect, then said: Look, does it work (solat) Sunnah? If the prayer is not perfect, then it is said. Then the other fardu practices are calculated (HR An-Nasa'i).

Prayer is a worship that must be performed by every Muslim individual. Perfect prayer can keep people from all wrongdoing. According to Mohd (2017), prayers can strengthen the faith and become self-shielding from the abusive and wrong practices. Abandoning the solat five times is deliberately sinful and Allah SWT has unveiled this ritual in the Qur'an that who abandon the solat five times deliberately will be rewarded with a

painful punishment not only in the world but also in the hereafter. Therefore, Muslims must remember each other not to abandon what is governed by Allah S.W.T. Do not abandon the five-day prayer which is the fortress and strength of ukhuwah between the servant and the Creator. Hence, let us both perform this fardu solely with sincerity and perfection. But how sad when we see a future generation who refuses to bow to the Creator by ignoring this mandatory practice. In fact, this issue needs to be further from the primary school so it will not spread to high school and higher levels.

In addition, the problem arises when there are Year Three pupils in the school who are still not fluent and do not master the reading in the prayer (Rukun Qauli). This can be detected when they take a long time to prepare each time they are tested especially during the prayer test of prayer. This problem becomes very complicated when the teachers perform a reading test in the practice of fardu prayer. If the students practice fardu prayers five times a day yesterday istiqamah or persistent, they will not take a long time to prepare the recitation of the recitation in the prayer. The ignorance or lack of understanding of the practice of prayer is also one of the factors that cause them to do not pray. They are also less interested and lazy and do not have the passion for knowledge creation especially religious knowledge and deep knowledge of Islam. This ignorance caused them to not perform prayer.

Thus, this study looks at whether the educational status, religious knowledge and family economy, affect the practice of the prayer of the Setiu District Primary Schools.

The method used is quantitative. Data were analyzed using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) with IBM-SPSS-AMOS program version 21.0. SEM is formed with two main models namely measurement model and Structural model. Before the SEM test is tested, prior adjustment tests should be made to ensure that the tested indicator actually represents the measured construct. There are two analyzes as prerequisites that must be met before the SEM analysis is performed: (1) Exploration Analysis Factor (EFA), and (2) Confirmation Factor Analysis (CFA). Validation factor analysis (CFA) is a test of measurement model to ensure that each construct meets procedures such as validity and reliability for each experiment being built (Kline, 2016; Awang, 2015; Chua, 2014d; Byrne, 2013; Hair et al., 2006; Schumucker & Lomax, 2004). Comparison of model measurement is essential to ensure that any latent construct in this study is compatible with the data studied before SEM can be continued.

Using the CFA method can assess the extent to which factors are observed significantly to the latent construct used. This assessment is done by examining the stiffness value of the regression pathway from factor to observed variable (factor loading) rather than the relationship between factors (Byrne, 2001). Through the use of CFA, any item not conforming to the

measurement model is derived from the model. This inequality is due to the low load factor value. Researchers need to apply the CFA process to all model-related construct, either separately or collectively (combined CFA models) (Alias & Hartini, 2017). The compatibility of the hypothetical models tested is verified using the Fitness Indexes to see the values of Root Mean Square Error of Approximation ($RMSEA < 0.08$), Goodness of Fit Index ($GFI > 0.90$), Comparative Fit Index ($CFI > 0.90$) and Chi Square/Degree of Freedom ($\chi^2/df < 5.0$). According to Hair et al. (2006) if the value of χ^2 is less than 2.00 but significant, it should be noted whether the sample is large or vice versa. Sample size above 200 can cause χ^2 to be significant. Therefore, Hair and his colleagues propose two other indices namely CFI and RMSEA to ensure CFA analysis establishes a dimensionless research model. If the CFI value exceeds 0.90 and the RMSEA is less than 0.08 it is said that the existence of Unidimensionality exists for the formation of each construct.

Discussion

Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA)

There are two models that need to be analyzed in implementing the model of Structural Equation Modeling-SEM Measurement Model and Structural Model. Awang (2015), Hoque et al., (2017) and Chik & Abdullah (2018) suggests two steps to follow Structured Equation Modeling (SEM).

- Verification of the Measurement Model of all constructs involved through the CFA method.
- Model all constructs into Structural Models and Modeling Structural Equations.

A lot of researcher Measurement Model in accordance with the research data is important to verify the SEM (Awang, 2014; Awang et al., 2015a; Hoque et al., 2017; Kashif et al., 2016; Chik & Abdullah, 2018). If the Measurement Model does not match the data from the field, the Built-in Structured Equation Model is invalid. Therefore, the first step in SEM analysis is to determine the Measurement Model according to the data from the field. Model Compatibility Model Measurements with field data were performed using CFA. Through the CFA approach, researchers examined statistically to validate the proposed construction model.

- a) Validity and Reliability Test Model:** Before evaluating the compatibility of built models, assessments for Unidimensionality, Validity, and Reliability Models The measurements of this study should be carried out first. Here's a little introduction to Unidimensionality, Validity and Reliability.
- b) Not Dimensionless:** this requirement can be satisfied through a product deletion procedure that has a weighted value factor. Low Factor Loading to achieve a set of Fitness Index. Goods with a weight value of less than 0.6 are considered unimportant for

construct and need to be released (Kashif et al., 2016).

- c) **Validity:** there are three types of validity to be achieved with constructive models of Construct Validity, Convergence Validity, and Discriminant Validation.
- d) **Construct Validity:** Construct Validity refers to the accuracy of the measuring instrument used to measure the construct intended in this study. The construct validity explains the extent to which a statement in the item used can measure the constructs that the researcher wants to measure. Conformity is achieved when all Fitness Indexes for development meet the specified level. Table 1 shows the three categories of compatibility indexes that must be achieved by building Absolute Fit, Incremental Fit and Parsimonious Fit models.

Table 1: Three Compatibility Index Categories as well as Recognized Index Types (Awang, 2015)

Name of Category	Name of Index	Level of Acceptance
Absolute Fit Index	RMSEA	RMSEA < 0.08
	GFI	GFI > 0.90
Incremental Fit Index	AGFI	AGFI > 0.90
	CFI	CFI > 0.90
	IFI	IFI > 0.90
	TLI	TLI > 0.90
	NFI	NFI > 0.90
Parsimonious Fit Index	Chisq/df	Chi-Square/ df < 3.0

*** Index is always used by researchers.

- e) **Convergence Validity:** Convergent validity refers to the relevance of the measurement model to other theoretical measurement models. Validity Building a construct will be achieved if all Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values reach a minimum of 0.50 (Hoque et al., 2017).
- f) **Discriminant Validity:** Discriminant validity illustrates the extent to which the construct has no overlapping relationship with other constructs in the same model so that it can be said to be excessive from other constructs (Kashif et al., 2016). The validity of

discrimination is assessed through the Discrimination Validity Summary Index. The discriminant validity of the construct can be achieved if all diagonal matrix values are greater than the other values in row cells and column cells. The diagonal value of the matrix is the square root of the extracted average variance (AVE) while the value in the matrix is the correlation between the strings in the model (Hoque et al., 2017).

- g) Reliability:** SEM does not adopt Internal Reliability measurements or Internal Reliability as measured by Cronbach Alpha value. In contrast SEM adopts Reliability Composite value measured by CR value and also Average Value of Variance Extracted (AVE). There are two criteria to verify the reliability of the Measurement Model in this study:
- h) Reliability Composite (CR):** CR values are measured using the Factor Loading factor of each item in construct. Each Latent construct must achieve a minimum CR value of 0.60 ($CR > 0.6$) to be considered as having achieved Composite Reliability (Awang et al., 2015a).
- i) Average Variations Extracted or Average Variance Exceeded (AVE):** The AVE value is also calculated by using the Factor Loading factor of each item under construct. The AVE value needs to reach

the minimum limit of 0.50 (AVE>0.5) to prove the reliability of the latent construct model in this study that has been.

CFA Analysis for Conventional Educational Status Measurement Model

The Analysis of Fitness Index in Table 2 shows the Educational Status Construct Model has reached the level of Compatibility Index level as shown in Table 1 above. This means Building Validity for this construct has been achieved. The Measurement Model for the construct of Educational Status has reached the level of Compatibility Index. This means Building Validity for this construct has been achieved.

Table 2: Analysis to Determine Construct Validity

Name Category	Name Index	Index value	Research Findings
1. Absolute fit	RMSEA	0.069	Reached the set level
2. Incremental fit	CFI	0.992	Reached the set level
3. Parsimonious fit	ChiSq/df	2.221	Reached the set level

Figure 1: Layout Measurement Model for Educational Status

CFA Analysis for Religious Knowledge Construct

Measurement Model

The Analysis of the Fitness Index in Table 3 shows the Religious Knowledge Measurement Model has reached the level of Compatibility Level as shown in Table 1 above. This means Building Validity for this construct has been achieved (Kashif et al., 2016). The Measurement Model for Religious Knowledge construct has reached the level of Compatibility Index level. This means Building Validity for this construct has been achieved.

Table 3: Analysis to Determine Construct Validity

Name Category	Name Index	Index value	Research Findings
1. Absolute fit	RMSEA	0.070	Reached the set level

2. Incremental fit	CFI	0.985	Reached the set level
3. Parsimonious fit	ChiSq/df	2.251	Reached the set level

Figure 2: Layout Measurement Model for Religious Knowledge

CFA Analysis for Family Economy Model

The Analysis of Fitness Index in Table 4 shows Measurements of Constructive Model Family Economy has reached the level of Compatibility Level as shown in Table 1 above. This means Building Validity for this construction has been achieved. The Measurement Model for the construction of the Family Economy has reached the level of Compatibility Index. This means Building Validity for this construct has been achieved.

Figure 3: Layout Measurement Models of Family Economy

Table 4: Analysis to Determine Construct Validity

Name Category	Name Index	Index value	Research Findings
1. Absolute fit	RMSEA	0.048	Reached the set level
2. Incremental fit	CFI	0.996	Reached the set level
3. Parsimonious fit	ChiSq/df	1.595	Reached the set level

CFA Analysis for Student Prayer Practice Model

The Analysis of Fitness Index in Table 5 shows Measurements of Constructive Model Student Prayer Practice has reached the level level of Compatibility Level as shown in

Table 1 above. This means Building Validity for this construction has been achieved. The Measurement Model for the construction of the Student Prayer Practice has reached the level of Compatibility Index. This means Building Validity for this construct has been achieved.

Figure 4: Layout Measurement Models of Student Prayer Practice

Table 5: Analysis to Determine Construct Validity

Name Category	Name Index	Index value	Research Findings
1. Absolute fit	RMSEA	0.063	Reached the set level
2. Incremental fit	CFI	0.990	Reached the set level

3. Parsimonious fit	ChiSq/df	2.026	Reached the set level
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Confirmation Factor Analysis of All Measurement Models (Pooled CFA)

The Confirmation Factor Analysis (CFA) is required to evaluate the correlation value between constructs in the Discriminant Validity procedure. If the correlation value between constructs exceeds 0.85, both constructs are said to be excessive. The procedural findings of Combined Factor Confirmation (Pooled CFA) are shown in Figure 5. As always, the value on a single-headed arrow is the weighting factor of each item, while the value on the double-headed arrow is the correlation between the constructs. Through the Combined Validity Factor Analysis method, only one model of the compatibility index represents all the constructed constructs. The findings from Table 6 show the three categories of model compatibility indexes for all constructs model have been achieved.

Figure 5: Findings of Results from the CFA Construct Combinations Procedure (Pooled Construct CFA)

Table 6: Comparison of Value Index Models for Three Compatibility Categories

Name Category	Name Index	Index value	Research Findings
1. Absolute fit	RMSEA	0.067	Reached the set level
2. Incremental fit	CFI	0.960	Reached the set level

3. Parsimonious fit	ChiSq/df	2.148	Reached the set level
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Another requirement of the validity that all constructs in the model need is Discrimination Validity. Discriminatory validity is necessary to prove that all constructs in the model do not have a strong relationship with each other causing multicollinearity problems (Chik & Abdullah, 2018). This verification requires researchers to develop the Discrimination Index Validity Summary table.

Table 7: Summary of Discrimination Validity Index

Construct	Education al status	Religious Knowled ge	Family Econom y	Stude nt Praye r Pract ice
Educational status	0.834			
Religious Knowledge	0.530	0.820		
Family Economy	0.380	0.710	0.851	
Student Prayer Practice	0.500	0.760	0.700	0.849

Table 7 shows the Summary of Discrimination Validity Index among all constructs in the model. Root values of the Index of Concentration Validity (AVE) for each construct on the diagonal matrix. Another value in the table is the correlation between the two constructs. Discrimination Validity will be achieved if all the root values of convergence validity (AVE) (Diagonal) are greater than other values of both rows and columns. Findings from Table 7 show Discrimination Validity for all constructions in the model achieved.

Analysis of the Impact between Constructs Educational Status, Religious Knowledge and Family Economy on Student Prayer Practice

Analysis by using SEM yields a standard regression value between the construct and the usual regression value and both have their own utility. Figure 6 shows the standardized estimates regression weight findings, whereas Figure 7 shows a typical unstandardized estimates regression value as a result of the SEM procedure. An important summary of the SEM findings in Figure 6 (standardized estimates regression):

- 1) The value of R^2 to build Student Prayer Practice (SPP) is 0.67. This shows three constructs of predictors in the model (see arrow), namely Educational Status (ES), Religious Knowledge (RK) and Family Economy (FE)

contributing 67% to Student Prayer Practice (SPP) among the populations in the study.

2) The correlation value between two free constructs on the model shown by double-headed arrows is as follows. The correlation between ES and RK is 0.47, ES and FE is 0.42 and RK and FE is 0.70. This shows that the SEM model is valid and has no multicollinearity problem.

Figure 6: SEM Findings Indicate the Standardized Regression Value between Constructs

Figure 7: SEM Findings Indicate the Unstandardized Regression Value between Constructs

Figure 7 shows the findings of regression values between the constructs in the model, to build the required regression equation and to test the next hypothesis. An important summary of the SEM findings in Figure 7 (Unstandardized estimates regression value). Regression equations for ES, RK, FE and SPP are as follows:

$$SPP = 0.19ES + 0.46RK + 0.27FE (R^2 = 0.67)$$

Furthermore, the researcher will test every hypothesis proposed in this research. Table 8 shows the approximation of the direct effects of the effects of each independent construct on the dependent construct in the model as shown in Figure 6 above.

Table 8: Regression Coefficients between Construct Value and Probability (p)

Constr uct		Constr uct	Estima te	S.E.	C.R .	P	Label
SPP	< -- -	ES	0.191	0.06 0	3.19 3	0.00 1	Signific ant
SPP	< -- -	RK	0.456	0.07 2	6.35 0	0.00 1	Signific ant
SPP	< -- -	FE	0.270	0.06 6	4.06 5	0.00 1	Signific ant

*** Significant value at the level of significance, $p < 0.001$

Table 8 shows the results of hypothesis testing of the direct effect of independent construct on dependent construct. Hypothesis testing in Table 9 is based on the SEM findings from Figure 6 above.

Table 9: Hypothesis Test of Direct Impact between Constructs

Direct Effect Hypothesis	P	Decision
H ₁ : The status of family education has a significant direct impact on the practices of the Setiu District Primary School students	0.001	Supported
H ₂ : Family religious knowledge has a significant direct impact on the practices of the Setiu District Primary School students.	0.001	Supported
H ₃ : The family economy has a significant direct impact on the practice of prayer of the Setiu District Primary school students.	0.001	Supported

Impact of Educational Status on Student Prayer Practice

Table 8 shows that Educational status has a significant direct impact on the Student Prayer Practice with estimated regression value (β) is 0.191 at significant level 0.001 (Estimate=0.191, CR=3.193, $p < 0.001$). This means that the construct of Educational status has a positive and significant influence on the construct of Student Prayer Practice. This means that if the Educational status increased by 1 unit, the Student

Prayer Practice will increase by 0.191 units. The findings of this study indicate that the construct of Educational status has a positive and significant influence on the construct of Student Prayer Practice.

Impact of Religious Knowledge on Student Prayer Practice

Table 8 shows that Religious Knowledge has a significant direct impact on the Student Prayer Practice with an estimate of regression value (β) is 0.456 at a significant level of 0.001, (Estimate=0.456, CR=6.350, $p < 0.001$). This means that the construct of Religious Knowledge has a positive and significant influence on the construct of Student Prayer Practice. This means that if the Religious Knowledge increases by 1 unit, the Student Prayer Practice will increase by 0.456 units. The findings of this study indicate that the construct of Religious Knowledge has a positive and significant influence on the construct of Student Prayer Practice.

Impact of Family Economy on Student Prayer Practice

Table 8 shows that the Family Economy has a significant direct impact on the Student Prayer Practice with an estimate of regression value (β) is 0.270 at a significant level of 0.001 (Estimation=0.270, CR=4.065, $p < 0.001$). This means that the construct of Family Economy has a positive and significant influence on the construct of Student Prayer Practice. This means that if the Family Economy increased by 1 unit, Student Prayer Practice will increase by 0.270 units. The findings of this study

indicate that the construct of Family Economy has a positive and significant influence on the construct of Student Prayer Practice.

Conclusion

Overall, the CFA analysis carried out on the measurement model for the construction of educational status, religious knowledge, family economy and student prayer practice, has been shown to have reached the fitness index. While the combined factorization analysis of all measurement models (Pooled CFA) shows that the three categories of model compatibility indexes for all models of constructs have been achieved and discriminant validity for all constructs in the model has also been achieved. Inference analysis findings also show educational status, religious knowledge and family economy, have a positive and significant influence on student prayer practice. This shows that family education, especially in religious knowledge and economic family, plays a role in the practice of prayer in primary schools.

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